

STUDY OF EFFECT OF FIVE DIFFERENT PARAMETERS ON THE NICKEL IONS REMOVAL FROM THE WASTEWATER USING A CHEMICAL MODIFIED ADSORBENT BASED ON CHIA SEED MUCILAGE

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Abstract

The current study addresses the impact of five key operation parameters on nickel (Ni^{2+}) ion removal in wastewater using chemically modified chia seed mucilage adsorbent. The parameters analyzed are temperature, contact time, solution pH, adsorbent dosage, and concentration of Ni(II) ion. Chemical modification has been performed on the adsorbent to increase its surface functionality, active binding sites, and overall adsorption capacity. Adsorption isotherms and kinetic models were used to analyze the results of the batch adsorption tests which were carried out to determine the impact of each parameter systematically. The results showed that the rate of Ni^{2+} removal was influenced by the dosage of adsorbent used, the condition of the adsorbent (the proper pH), and the duration of contact however the initial concentration of sample and the temperature influenced differently on the process of adsorption. Under ideal conditions, maximum removal efficiency was achieved, which demonstrated that the chemically modified adsorbent is more efficient than a chemically treated one. This study shows that the modified adsorbent would be an effective, cheap and acceptable material in the treatment of industrial wastewater to remove Ni^{2+} .

INTRODUCTION

Industrial effluents from operations including electroplating, battery manufacturing, metal surface treatment, mining, and chemical production frequently contain nickel (Ni^{2+}), a heavy metal (Wang et al., 2024). Ni^{2+} ions in wastewater pose a severe environmental issue since it poses toxicological hazards including impaired renal functioning, respiratory complications, and carcinogenicity, particularly

with improper treatment. Moreover, Ni^{2+} ions can accumulate in living organisms and have a long-term ecological impact due to non-biodegradable nature (Noman et al., 2022). Conventional techniques for extracting Ni^{2+} from wastewater include chemical precipitation, ion exchange, membrane filtration, coagulation/flocculation, and reverse osmosis. However, many of these procedures are

hampered by high operating costs, the creation of secondary hazardous sludge, and limited efficiency, particularly when metal concentrations are low (Zinicovscaia et al., 2020). Among the alternatives, adsorption has gained popularity because to its high removal efficiency, cost, and ease of usage (Raval et al., 2016; Hussain et al., 2021; Hussain et al. 2023; Ali et al., 2025; Shehzad et al., 2025).

Over the years, a variety of adsorbents have been studied for the removal of Ni²⁺ ions. These include low-cost natural materials (such agricultural wastes), biosorbents, nanotechnology, and activated carbons. For example, biosorption using plant biomass, such Aloe vera leaf residue, has shown promising Ni²⁺ absorption, which is strongly influenced by factors including temperature, pH, adsorbent dose, and contact time (Gupta and Kumar, 2019). Using chemically modified cellulose nanofibers derived from residual orange peel, a more recent work shown that surface functionalization significantly increases adsorption ability to enhance nickel removal (Matsedisho et al., 2025).

Adsorbents can be chemically modified in order to increase their adsorption properties. Indicatively, a copper-sulfate-ammonia complex has been utilized to treat activated carbon, enhance the absorption of Ni²⁺ by electrostatic interplay as well as surface complexation and cation exchange (Wang et al., 2024). Similarly, Ni²⁺ removal has been reported using hybrid adsorbents composed of a combination of biological materials (e.g., bacterial biofilm) and mineral supports (e.g., zeolite) with a removal efficiency of more than 100% at optimum pH (Zinicovscaia et al., 2020).

Regardless of the scope of the research, the performance of Ni²⁺ adsorption largely relies on the operation parameters including adsorbent dosage, initial metal concentration, pH, length of contact, and temperature. These aspects must be enhanced to achieve maximum elimination and to develop scalable, affordable treatment systems (Tao et al., 2016). Moreover, the polysaccharide based hydrogel are non-toxic, biocompatible, stimuli responsive, and chemically modifiable in nature. Hence their functional groups can be

alters by introducing anhydrides of acids on to its background (Irfan et al., 2021; Ali et al., 2022a, b; Bukhari et al., 2022; Ali et al., 2023a-d; Ali et al., 2024; Farid-ul-Haq et al., 2024; Amjad et al., 2025, Khatoon et al., 2025).

Therefore, in this work, we investigate how five such variables, adsorbent dosage, initial Ni(II) concentration, solution pH, contact time, and temperature, affect the effectiveness of a chemically modified chia seed mucilage adsorbent intended for Ni²⁺ removal. Our goal is to determine the ideal circumstances for maximal Ni²⁺ absorption and to clarify the adsorption mechanisms involved by methodically examining their impact. The knowledge gathered from this study may greatly aid in the creation of effective and sustainable wastewater treatment methods for effluents polluted with Ni²⁺ ions.

2.1. Materials

Seeds of Chia were obtained from the local market in District Sargodha, Pakistan. All chemicals and reagents used in this study were of analytical grade (> 99% pure) and were used without further standardization or purification.

2.2. Extraction of mucilage and synthesis of adsorbent

The mucilage from the chia seeds was extracted through aqueous extraction procedure as previously reported by Khatoon et al., (2025). The mucilage was further modified using to prepare adsorbent material for the removal of Ni²⁺ ions from contaminated water was carried out by following the protocol reported by Ali et al., (2025) with slight modification.

2.3. Preparation of stock and working Ni(II) solutions

First of a stock solution of 1000 mg L⁻¹ Ni²⁺ was prepared by dissolving an appropriate mass of Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O in deionized water (DI water) and making up to volume. Later, the working solutions containing desired initial concentrations were made by dilution method according to the given below equation.

$$C1V1=C2V2 \tag{1}$$

2.4. Pre-treatment of adsorbent

The adsorbent was completely dried at 60°C in an oven until constant weight was achieved and then sieve to get a fine size particle. The dry mass used for each experiment was noted and recorded.

2.5. General batch adsorption procedure

Adsorption experiments were performed at standard conditions, i.e., initial Ni²⁺ concentration 100 mg L⁻¹, adsorbent dose 20 mg g⁻¹, pH 6, temperature 298K, and contact time 20 min. To do so, Erlenmeyer flasks used for each experiment were labelled as 100 mL. Pipette out 100 mL of Ni(II) working solution (known initial concentration C₀) into each flask. Then adjust the solution pH to the required value using 0.1 M HCl or 0.1 M NaOH; measure with pH meter. Add the pre-weighed amount of adsorbent to each flask (e.g., 20 mg/g L⁻¹ in 100 mL). Start timer immediately. The flask were placed in thermostatic shaker set to required temperature and agitation speed. At pre-determined sampling times or after equilibrium time, withdraw samples: removed the flask and separate solid from liquid by centrifugation (e.g., 4000 rpm for 5-10 min) or by filtration (0.45 µm). The supernatant/filtrate were collected in clean vials for Ni²⁺ analysis on FAAS. The effect of pH, Initial Ni²⁺ concentration, adsorbent dose, time, and temperature were studied on the adsorption capacity.

2.7. Calculations

The following formulas were used to calculate the adsorption capacity in g/g and in percentage.

$$q_e = \frac{C_i - C_e}{m} \times V \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Cd(II) adsorption capacity (\%)} = \frac{C_i - C_e}{C_i} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effect of pH on Ni²⁺ adsorption

The chemically modified adsorbent's capacity and adsorption effectiveness toward Ni²⁺ ions were

significantly influenced by the pH of the solution. The adsorption of Ni²⁺ was considerably decreased at lower pH levels (below pH 3). The high concentration of hydrogen ions (H⁺), which fiercely fight with Ni²⁺ for the accessible active binding sites on the adsorbent surface, is responsible for this decrease (Foo and Hameed, 2010). The adsorbent's surface gets protonated in acidic environments, creating a net positive charge. Effective adsorption is limited as a result of significant electrostatic repulsion between the positively charged surface and the Ni²⁺ ions. Ni²⁺ uptake significantly improved when the pH rose near neutrality. The modified adsorbent's functional groups underwent deprotonation at a pH that was mildly acidic to nearly neutral (usually between 4 and 6), which led to the formation of negatively charged sites. Strong electrostatic attraction and complexation with Ni²⁺ ions were made possible by these negatively charged surface groups, such as -COO⁻, -OH⁻, or other functional moieties added during chemical modification (Dimpe et al., 2017). As a result, in this pH range, the adsorption capacity and % removal both significantly enhanced. However, the possible development of nickel hydroxide precipitates (Ni(OH)₂), which artificially enhance apparent removal without representing genuine adsorption, made it unable to reliably quantify a further rise in adsorption at pH levels above 6. Consequently, the range where the adsorbent surface is sufficiently deprotonated but metal precipitation has not yet taken place is the ideal pH for Ni²⁺ adsorption. The hypothesis that the adsorption process comprises surface complexation and electrostatic attraction, both of which are significantly influenced by the protonation state of the adsorbent surface, is generally supported by the observed pH-dependent behaviour (Babel and Kurniawan, 2003). The chemically modified adsorbent functioned best at its optimal pH, highlighting the necessity of pH control for effective Ni²⁺ remediation.

Fig. 1: Effect of pH on adsorption capacity

3.2. Effect of initial Ni^{2+} concentration on adsorption capacity

The initial concentration of Ni^{2+} ions in the solution had a major impact on the chemically modified adsorbent's adsorption capability. The adsorption capacity (q_e) increased with the initial metal concentration. Large removal percentages but relatively low adsorption capacity values resulted from the numerous active functional groups on the adsorbent surface being able to bind efficiently since there were fewer metal ions in the solution at lower Ni^{2+} concentrations. However, when the initial concentration of Ni^{2+} increased, the driving force for mass transfer between the aqueous phase and the adsorbent surface grew, enhancing the diffusion of Ni^{2+} ions into pores and active sites. The adsorption capacity thus rose dramatically since there were

more ions available per unit (Ho and McKay, 1999). At very high concentrations, however, the rate of increase in adsorption capacity began to level off, indicating that the active adsorption sites were approaching saturation. Because there were insufficient accessible binding sites relative to the high concentration of metal ions, the percentage clearance of Ni^{2+} decreased in these conditions even while q_e stayed high. The adsorbent surface gradually gets saturated as concentration rises, which is compatible with Langmuir-type monolayer adsorption (Wu et al., 2018). These results demonstrate that maximal removal effectiveness is attained at intermediate concentrations when the adsorbent still has sufficient free active sites, even if high starting concentrations increase adsorption capacity.

Fig. 2: Effect of initial nickel concentration on adsorption capacity

3.3. Effect of Adsorbent Dose on Nickel Adsorption

The dosage of adsorbent greatly affected the efficacy of the removal of Ni^{2+} ions in aqueous solutions. The percentage of Ni^{2+} remove was strongly enhanced with the quantity of chemically modified adsorbent. This development is primarily due to the increased surface area and active adsorption sites that are achieved by the increased dose of adsorbents. The affinity of the system to absorb dissolved Ni^{2+} ions is increased with more accessible functional groups, including hydroxyl, carboxyl or other chemically added binding moieties (Vijayaraghavan et al., 2022). Reduced adsorbent doses lead to reduced removal as the number of active sites is not sufficient to capture Ni^{2+} ion in the solution. Even while the adsorption capacity per gram of adsorbent may remain relatively high due to saturation of accessible sites, the ratio of

metal ions to binding sites encourages incomplete adsorption. The increase in removal efficiency however begins to level off with increasing adsorbent dosage. This plateau effect occurs when the majority of Ni^{2+} ions in the solution are removed leaving a larger number of adsorption sites unused. Since metal ions are distributed over too many binding sites, the adsorption capacity (q_e) per unit mass of adsorbent decreases with increased dosage (Ofomaja and Naidoo, 2013). Overall, the results demonstrate that while very high doses reduce the efficacy of adsorption per gram of adsorbent, increasing the dosage of adsorbent increases the removal of Ni^{2+} to an optimal level by creating more active sites. These findings demonstrate how important it is to adjust adsorbent dosage in order to recover nickel from wastewater in an inexpensive and efficient manner.

Fig. 3: Effect of adsorbent dose on adsorption capacity

3.4. Effect of contact time on Ni²⁺ adsorption

Contact time largely controls the rate and volume of Ni²⁺ adsorption onto the chemically treated adsorbent. The results showed that Ni²⁺ removal increased rapidly during the initial stages of adsorption, particularly during the first 30 to 60 minutes. This rapid absorption is caused by a large number of open active sites and a strong driving force for mass transfer between the solution and the adsorbent surface. Ni²⁺ ions may now diffuse quickly and bind efficiently through ion exchange, electrostatic interactions, and surface complexation processes thanks to the chemically added functional groups (Weber and Morris, 1963). The adsorption rate reached equilibrium with increasing contact duration. As the majority of the available active sites were already occupied, this plateau stage shows that intraparticle diffusion and a decrease in the availability of the binding sites prevented further

adsorption. The equilibrium adsorption capacity (q_e) was constant, and the adsorption and desorption processes were at dynamic equilibrium. The time-dependent behavior observed is in agreement with pseudo-second-order kinetic models that suggest that the main process is chemisorption, i.e., exchange or sharing of electrons between Ni²⁺ ions and the functional groups on the adsorbent surface. The intraparticle diffusion model often has a multi-linear trend implying that both the pore diffusion and surface adsorption contribute to the process. Generally, the findings indicate that the altered adsorbent has a higher initial uptake, and a slower diffusion-controlled adsorption rate as the equilibrium is achieved, and that sufficient contact time is required to ensure maximum uptake of Ni²⁺. In real-world wastewater treatment applications, contact time optimization guarantees effective operation and minimizes needless processing time.

Fig. 4: Effect of contact time on adsorption capacity

3.5. Effect of temperature on Ni²⁺ adsorption

Ni²⁺ ion adsorption onto the chemically modified adsorbent was significantly influenced by temperature. The adsorption capacity gradually increased as the temperature rose from lower to moderate values. This pattern indicates that the adsorption process is at least somewhat endothermic as higher temperatures increase Ni²⁺ ion mobility, decrease boundary layer resistance, and accelerate the rate at which metal ions diffuse into the pores and active sites of the adsorbent. Increased accessibility of adsorption sites may also result from a little expansion of pore structures caused by high temperatures. Nevertheless, the adsorption performance either plateaued or slightly declined at very high temperatures. This decrease might be explained by the reduction of electrostatic forces and metal-

ligand interactions between Ni²⁺ ions and functional groups on the modified adsorbent surface. Reduced binding strength can also result from excessive heating that compromises the structural integrity of certain surface groups (Boparai et al., 2011). Furthermore, a high temperature may counteract the adsorption effect by increasing the likelihood of desorption. Overall, the temperature-dependent response indicates that while extremely high temperatures may decrease adsorbate-adsorbent interactions, moderate heating increases ion mobility and site accessibility to increase Ni²⁺ absorption. Determining the ideal temperature range is therefore crucial for optimizing effectiveness and guaranteeing the long-term stability of the modified adsorbent in real-world wastewater treatment applications (Wierzba, 2017).

Fig. 5: Effect of contact time on adsorption capacity

4. Conclusion

The present research shows that chemically modified adsorbents offer a highly efficient and sustainable method of removing Ni^{2+} in wastewater. Following the systematic evaluation of five fundamental operating parameters, the adsorbent dosage, the initial solution concentration of Ni^{2+} , pH, adsorption contact time, and the temperature were identified as the most important factors influencing adsorption behavior. The result showed that Ni^{2+} adsorption is maximized by using adjusted pH and sufficient contact time despite the fact that high dosage of an adsorbent increases the removal efficiency by increasing the number of active binding sites. Even though the percentage of removal in the saturation effects is reduced by an increase in starting concentration of metal, the chemically functionalized adsorbent proved to be of high capacity and high affinity under optimal conditions. Patterns that are temperature dependent gave additional evidence that the adsorption process may be both chemical and

physical. The results of the research prove that chemical modification significantly enhances the performance and functioning of adsorbent surface compared to untreated ones. This study not only demonstrates the possibilities of the improved adsorbent as a low cost option to treat industrial wastewater, but it also offers practical data in the development of adsorption-based systems. Future research can be based on the regeneration cycles, column-based applications, and real-wastewater testing to determine the long-term practical applicability.

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